

Inhibitory effect of *Ricinus communis* (Castor-oil plant) leaf extract on corrosion of mild steel in low chloride medium

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Plant extract *Ricinus communis* was tested for its inhibitory effects towards mild steel in 100 ppm sodium chloride. The corrosion behaviour of plant extract (*Ricinus communis*) was studied by means of electrochemical polarization and impedance measurements. It was found from weight loss measurements that the inhibition efficiency was about 84% in 300 ppm of the plant extract. Polarization measurements indicated that the plant extracts generally act as cathodic inhibitors on the fourth day. Electrochemical impedance results also showed that the natural plant extract increases the corrosion resistance of mild steel. Results of our study from polarization and electrochemical impedance measurements indicated that *Ricinus communis* might alleviate the corrosion process in mild steel.

There was considerable recent interest over investigation on the corrosion and or corrosion inhibiting properties of plant extracts, such as tannin, cassava juice, etc.¹. The presence of tannin in the solution extracts was associated with the corrosion inhibition effect of the different plants extracts investigated². Water extract of Henna (*Lawsonia inermis*) leaves powder was evaluated as corrosion inhibitor for steel and aluminium in saline, acidic and alkaline water³. The effect of nicotinic acid, niocotinamide and nictotine on the corrosion behavior of iron in Na₂SO₄ and NaCl solution was investigated⁴.

Since alkaloids are good inhibitors, present in plants, it was thought to be of interest to study some plant materials as inhibitors for the corrosion of mild steel in acid media⁵. Preceding work on the aqueous extracts of karkade, pomegrate fruit peels, tamarind fruits tea leaves and beat revealed high efficiencies in retarding the dissolution of steel in NaOH⁶.

The aim of this study was to investigate the ethanolic extract of *Ricinus communis* as corrosion inhibitor in neutral aqueous environment. Mild steel was immersed in 100 ppm of sodium chloride and evaluated against various concentrations of ethanolic extracts of *Ricinus communis*.

Results and discussion

The potentiodynamic polarization curves on the fourth

day in presence and absence of the plant extract are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. It can be seen from Table 1 that the corrosion current decreases in presence of various concentrations of the plant extract. Also the potential of mild steel in presence of the plant extract shifted to negative side on the 4th

Fig. 1. Anodic potentiostatic polarization of mild steel in 100 ppm sodium chloride containing various concentrations of *Ricinus communis* on 4th day : (O) control, (●) 300 ppm, (□) 100 ppm, (■) 500 ppm.

Table 1. Anodic and cathodic current density, anodic and cathodic Tafel slope of mild steel in 100 ppm NaCl in presence of various plant extracts evaluated by anodic polarization techniques

System	Concentration ppm	Anodic potential (mV vs SCE)	Anodic current density ($\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$)	Anodic b_c (mV/dec)	Cathodic potential (mV vs SCE)	Cathodic current density ($\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$)	Cathodic b_c (mV/dec)
Control		-677.6	3.850	34	-683.8	3.62	33
<i>Ricinus communis</i>	100 ppm	-707	1.910	39	-703	2.22	56
	300 ppm	-708	1.000	21	-696	1.93	50
	500 ppm	-713	2.020	48	-708	1.42	44

Fig. 2. Cathodic potentiostatic polarization of mild steel in 100 ppm sodium chloride containing various concentrations of *Ricinus communis* on 4th day : (O) control, (●) 300 ppm, (□) 100 ppm, (■) 500 ppm.

day. The significant reduction of anodic and cathodic current might be due to the adsorption of mixed inhibitors, present in the plant extract.

Fig. 3. Nyquist plot of mild steel in 100 ppm sodium chloride containing various concentrations of *Ricinus communis* on 4th day : (a) Control, (b) 100 ppm, (c) 300 ppm, (d) 500 ppm.

The selected plant is known to have carbon, nitrogen, oxygen and phosphorus based organic compounds with calcium, magnesium and traces of metals like zinc and iron etc.⁷. It can be assumed that the presence of organic compounds (phosphorus based) may act as anodic inhibitor

while calcium, magnesium and nitrogenous may act as cathodic inhibitor.

The impedance measurements are presented as Nyquist plot in Fig. 3 on the fourth day, in the absence and presence of aqueous extracts. R_{ct} values have increased in presence of the inhibitor system, indicating that they are corrosion inhibitive in nature (Table 2). The C_{dl} and the surface coverage values in presence of different concentrations of the plant extract are also given in Table 2.

The nature of impedance curves reveals that the plant extracts control both activation and diffusion reactions which supports the polarization curves. It can be concluded that the plant extract acts as mixed inhibitor and control the both anodic (activation) and cathodic (diffusion) reactions.

Table 2. Corrosion resistance and surface coverage of mild steel in 100 ppm NaCl in presence of various plant extracts evaluated by impedance studies

System	Concentration ppm	R_{ct} (Kohn.cm ²)	$10^4.C_{dl}$ ($\mu\text{F}/\text{cm}^2$)	Surface coverage θ
Control		0.7	14.40	
<i>Ricinus communis</i>	100 ppm	0.6	7.56	0.25
	300 ppm	1.1	3.00	0.79
	500 ppm	1.3	3.57	0.75

The inhibitive action of *Ricinus communis* plant extract is due to the strong chemisorption of the phytochemical constituents of the extract especially heterocyclic ingredients on the surface the mild steel. From the electro chemical studies, it is evident that this eco-friendly biodegradable inhibitor acts through mixed mode of inhibition. Hence it can be concluded that extract of the plant forming a film protects the metal and it also act as eco-friendly component.

Experimental

The leaves of the *Ricinus communis* were collected and dried at room temperature. Air dried plants were extracted successively with ethanol (60–80°C) for 6 h. The solution was filtered and distilled at 70–80°C, to remove ethanol from the plant extract and the concentrate is used as the in-

hibiting chemical. Concentrating of the ethanol extract and consequent cooling in the ice-chest deposited a small quantity of reddish brown coloured solid which was stored in refrigerator. By using this concentrated extract the following experiments were carried out.

Electrochemical measurement were carried out with mild steel specimens of 1 cm² area as the working electrode. The surface of the specimens were mechanically polished and degreased with trichloroethylene. Saturated calomel electrode and platinum foil were used as reference and counter electrode respectively. The basic solution was 100 ppm in Cl⁻ to which the additives were added in varying concentration (100, 300, 500 ppm). Potentialdynamic polarization curves were plotted using potential scanning rate of 1 mV s⁻¹. Both the anodic and cathodic branches of polarizations curves were recorded. Impedance measurements were carried out at open circuit potential (OCP) 1 h after immersion of the electrode in the test solution. The AC frequency range studied was 10 kHz to 100 mHz. BAS-IM6 Electrochemical Analyzer (USA) was used for the electrochemical measurements.

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